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Assessing the Effect of Chief Executive Officer's Personality on Employee Performance in Small and Medium-Size Enterprises

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Abstract:

This research, titled "Assessing the Impact of Chief Executive Officer's Personality on Employee Performance in Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs)," investigates the relationship between CEO personality traits and employee performance in SMEs. The study arose from the recognition that many SMEs struggle to achieve their performance goals, often due to factors such as ineffective leadership. A quantitative research approach was employed, involving a purposive sample of 380 employees from selected SMEs in Yaoundé. The data collection was conducted using a structured questionnaire based on a 5-point Likert scale, designed to assess CEO personality traits (observable features, psychological characteristics, social attributes, and professionalism) and their effects on employee performance. The collected data was analyzed using exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to examine the underlying relationships between the variables and multiple regression analysis to test the significance of these relationships. The findings confirmed a significant positive relationship between CEO personality traits and employee performance, supporting the hypotheses that observable features (e.g., age, gender), psychological characteristics (e.g., agreeableness, emotional stability), social attributes (e.g., being a good listener, approachable), and professionalism (e.g., education, punctuality) of CEOs all positively impact employee performance. Specifically, the regression analysis revealed that each CEO personality trait had a significant influence on employee performance, with p-values for all hypotheses being less than 0.05 (H1: 0.0430, H2: 0.000, H3: 0.005, H4: 0.0458), indicating strong support for the research hypotheses. Based on these results, the study recommends that CEOs and organizational leaders develop and enhance traits such as emotional stability, intellectual capacity, and strong interpersonal skills, as these can positively influence employee motivation and organizational success.

Keywords: Chief Executive Officer, Employee Performance, SMEs, Leadership, Organizational Success

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid expansion of globalization, coupled with the swift advancement of information and communication technologies, has resulted in a dynamic and often unpredictable business environment (Lincoln, 2010). In this increasingly competitive landscape, organizations face unprecedented pressures, with strategic management playing a pivotal role in wealth creation (Lincoln, 2010). Theories on strategic management emphasize the critical influence of senior leadership, particularly Chief Executive Officers (CEOs) and Senior Management Teams (TMTs), on both the strategic direction and performance outcomes of firms (Hambrick & Mason, 1984). Specifically, the Upper Echelons Theory posits that the characteristics of CEOs, such as their personal traits, affect strategic decisions and organizational outcomes (Hambrick & Mason, 1984). As a result, several studies

have investigated the impact of demographic factors on CEOs, including age, experience, educational background, socio-economic status, and financial position (Waldman et al., 2001).

Beyond demographic influences, extensive research has explored the significance of CEO leadership in shaping organizational performance (Agle et al., 2006; Ling et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2011). However, while studies have often focused on leadership styles at lower levels of management due to limited data on top executives, there is an increasing recognition of the need to examine different leadership approaches, including those specifically related to business leadership, as proposed by Pawar and Eastman (1997). This contrasts with leadership styles often described as "generous" or "flexible," which, while important, do not always address the unique challenges of business leadership (Pawar & Eastman, 1997).

Recent research on the relationship between CEO leadership style and employee performance has produced mixed findings. Some studies suggest a positive relationship, indicating that CEO leadership significantly enhances performance (Carmeli et al., 2011; Elenkov, 2002), while others find no support for such claims (Tosi et al., 2004; Waldman et al., 2001). The inconsistency in these findings may be attributed to variations in performance measurement metrics and organizational contexts (Tosi et al., 2004). Specifically, scholars have argued that the impact of CEO leadership on performance is contingent on the level of environmental uncertainty faced by the firm (Tosi et al., 2004; Waldman et al., 2001, 2004). In relatively stable organizational contexts, senior executives may have more freedom to shape strategic direction, thereby exerting greater influence on firm performance. This notion is further supported by Lubatkin et al. (2006), who suggest that CEOs of small, privately owned firms may have a more pronounced impact on the organization compared to their counterparts in larger firms.

Moreover, the leadership style of founding CEOs has been identified as an important factor influencing firm performance. Ling et al. (2008) found that the correlation between CEO leadership style changes and strong performance is more robust in firms led by founding CEOs than those with non-founding CEOs. While numerous studies on CEO leadership and firm performance have been conducted in countries such as the United States (Agle et al., 2006), England (Ling et al., 2008), and China (Wang et al., 2011), there is a notable gap in research examining foreign firms.

The role of CEOs is also central to ongoing debates in both academic and policy circles. A growing body of literature suggests that CEO identity and behavior play a critical role in driving firm performance (Bertrand & Schoar, 2003; Bennesen et al., 2007; Kaplan et al., 2012). This raises the question of how differences in CEO behavior relate to variations in employee performance. Scholars have approached these questions from two distinct perspectives. On one hand, Mintzberg (1973) and others have analyzed the real-time behavior of CEOs through qualitative studies, offering valuable insights into management functions. However, these studies are often limited by small sample sizes and lack statistical rigor. On the other hand, economists have developed broader, albeit vague, categories of leadership styles, which are difficult to operationalize in empirical studies (Dessein & Santos, 2016; Hermalin, 1998, 2007).

1.2 Problem Statement

Performance in organizations, especially Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs), is influenced by a complex interplay of factors such as strategic direction, resource allocation, staff quality, and the business environment (Kotey & Slade, 2006; Prowse & Prowse, 2010). However, one of the most critical yet often overlooked factors is the personality of the Chief Executive Officer (CEO), who plays a central role in shaping the organizational culture, decision-making processes, and employee performance on a day-to-day basis (Hambrick & Mason, 1984; Judge & Bono, 2001). CEO leadership, which encompasses defining strategy, setting goals, motivating employees, and managing operations, is closely linked to the overall performance of the organization (Finkelstein & Hambrick, 1996).

In Cameroon, SMEs often face challenges of low productivity, inconsistent performance, and organizational inefficiency, which can be attributed to the CEO's leadership style and personality (Morris et al., 1997; Nwankwo, 2016). While the CEO's personality traits such as decisiveness, emotional intelligence, and communication style are known to influence leadership effectiveness (Goleman, 1998; Northouse, 2010), the

direct effect of these traits on employee performance in the context of SMEs remains underexplored (Waldman et al., 2001). Employee performance, including aspects such as creativity, job satisfaction, commitment, and productivity, can be significantly shaped by the CEO's approach to leadership (Bass, 1990; Tosi et al., 2004). However, there is a lack of empirical research examining this dynamic specifically in the Cameroonian SME context (Morris et al., 1997; Nwankwo, 2016).

Leadership is an interactive process that directly affects organizational success (Northouse, 2010). Studies have shown that CEOs who adopt transformational leadership styles linked to specific personality traits can drive higher levels of employee performance compared to those who rely on more transactional or commercial leadership approaches (Bass, 1990; Howell & Avolio, 1993). Transformational leadership, which emphasizes vision, motivation, and personalized consideration, has been found to enhance employee creativity, commitment, and performance (Judge & Piccolo, 2004; Kirkpatrick & Locke, 1996). In contrast, transactional leadership, which is more focused on rewards and punishments, tends to produce less innovative and committed employees (Bass, 1990; Lowe et al., 1996). Despite strong evidence supporting the link between CEO personality and performance (Lowe et al., 1996; Kirkpatrick & Locke, 1996), there is limited research examining this relationship within the SME sector, particularly in developing economies like Cameroon (Nwankwo, 2016).

Given the critical role of the CEO in shaping organizational outcomes, it is imperative to investigate how CEO personality influences employee performance in SMEs in Cameroon. Understanding this relationship will not only contribute to the broader leadership literature but will also offer practical insights for improving managerial practices in the SME sector, which is crucial for economic development in the region (Agle et al., 2006; Wang et al., 2011).

1.3 Aim of the Study

The aim of this study is to explore the impact of a CEO's personality traits on employee performance within Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Cameroon. Specifically, the study seeks to examine how the personality attributes of a CEO, such as emotional intelligence, decisiveness, and leadership style, influence key aspects of employee performance, including productivity, job satisfaction, creativity, and commitment. By understanding the relationship between CEO personality and employee performance, this research aims to provide insights that can guide both managers and policymakers in fostering leadership practices that enhance employee performance, drive organizational success, and improve the competitiveness of SMEs in Cameroon.

1.4 Research Objectives

1.4.1 Main Objective

To examine the influence of the CEO's personality on the performance of employees in Cameroon.

1.4.2 Specific Objectives

- i. To assess the influence of the observable features of the CEO on the employees' performance in Cameroon.
- ii. To analyze the impact of the CEO's psychological characteristics on the employees' performance in Cameroon.
- iii. To evaluate the impact of the social attributes of a CEO on the employees' performance in Cameroon.
- iv. To examine how the professionalism of a CEO can affect the employees' performance in Cameroon.

1.5 Research Questions

1.5.1 Main Research Question

What is the effect of a CEO's personality on the performance of employees in Cameroon?

1.5.2 Specific Research Questions

- i. What impact do the observable features of a CEO have on the employees' performance in Cameroon.?

- ii. Does the Psychological characteristics of a CEO affect the employees' performance in Cameroon.?
- iii. Does the social attributes of a CEO influence the performance of employees in Cameroon.?
- iv. To what extent does the professionalism of a CEO affect the employees' performance in Cameroon.?

1.6 Hypotheses

H1: There is a significant and positive relationship between observable features of the CEO and the employees' performance in Cameroon.

H2: There is a significant and positive relationship between CEO's psychological characteristics and the employees' performance in Cameroon.

H3: There is a significant and positive relationship between the social attributes of a CEO and the employees' performance in Cameroon.

H4: There is a significant and positive relationship between the professionalism of a CEO and the employees' performance in Cameroon.

1.6 LITERATURE REVIEW

1.6.1 The Chief Executive Officer (CEO)

The CEO plays a crucial role in organizational performance. According to the Upper Echelons Theory (Hambrick & Mason, 1984), senior management characteristics directly influence decision-making and organizational outcomes. The CEO's personality affects strategic decisions such as sales growth and return on investment (Peterson et al., 2003). Their behavior can shape the company's culture and affect how employees interact with each other (O'Reilly et al., 2014).

1.6.1.1 Psychological Characteristics

Research shows that CEO personality traits, like those defined by the **Big Five personality model** (Openness, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, Neuroticism), influence leadership effectiveness and organizational performance. CEOs with higher conscientiousness can help reduce silo effects in organizations, encouraging communication and collaboration (Schütz & Bloch, 2006).

1.6.1.2 Observable Characteristics

Studies show that observable CEO traits such as age, education, experience, and management tenure affect organizational behavior:

- i. **Age:** Older CEOs tend to make more cautious, risk-averse decisions compared to younger ones (Hambrick & Mason, 1984).
- ii. **Formal Education:** Higher education levels are associated with better strategic decision-making and higher firm performance (Wang et al., 2016).
- iii. **Management Experience:** A CEO's experience helps them evaluate alternatives better and make more informed strategic decisions (Simons et al., 1999).
- iv. **Management Tenure:** Longer CEO tenure can enhance employee relationships but also influence future company performance (Luo et al., 2014).

These factors can influence internal organizational elements like risk-taking, communication, and social integration (Eisenhardt & Schoonhoven, 1996).

1.6.2 CEO Leadership Behaviour

CEO leadership behavior, including **transformational** and **transactional** styles, also impacts organizational outcomes. Transformational leadership inspires employees by defining clear visions and showing commitment, whereas transactional leadership focuses on rewards and punishments to motivate employees (Yukl, 2002).

- i. **Transformational Leaders:** Often visionary, demonstrating trust and showing concern for employee development.

ii. **Transactional Leaders:** Focus on structure, ensuring compliance and achieving immediate goals. Both leadership styles influence organizational strategies and the CEO's effectiveness in motivating employees.

1.6.3 CEO Personality Characteristics

The Upper Echelons Theory suggests that a CEO's personality influences the organization's strategy and performance. For example, CEOs with narcissistic tendencies may show both strengths and weaknesses, which can shape the company's decisions in a complex way (Zhu & Chen, 2015). Research often links CEO traits to decisions about financial reporting, compensation, and investments (Hackbarth, 2008; Graham et al., 2013). Studies on the **Big Five** personality traits (Costa & McCrae, 1997) show that openness to experience is strongly linked to effective leadership, while high neuroticism might hinder performance.

1.6.4 CEO Gender and Earnings Management

The gender of a CEO can influence earnings management and organizational outcomes. Research shows that male CEOs may be more risk-prone, whereas female CEOs tend to adopt a more cautious and ethical approach (Faccio et al., 2016; Schubert, 2006). Female CEOs are less likely to manipulate earnings or take high risks, potentially enhancing long-term company value (Setyaningrum et al., 2019). However, gender-related studies on earnings management have produced mixed results across various industries.

1.6.5 The Importance of CEO and HRM Practices to Innovation

The CEO is crucial in driving innovation within the organization. In SMEs (Small and Medium Enterprises), the CEO's ability to lead and make strategic decisions directly influences the company's adoption of new technologies and business models (Lefebvre, 1992). Innovation can be categorized into product innovation and process innovation, which require specific knowledge, skills, and expertise (Lopez-Cabralez et al., 2009). HRM practices, such as training, team collaboration, and knowledge-sharing, are vital for fostering innovation. HRM processes enhance the firm's capacity to innovate by encouraging knowledge flow and rewarding incremental improvements (Laursen, 2002).

1.7 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study aims to identify the different types of factors related to business leadership provided by the CEO and how it affects employees and their performance. The concept is based on the relationship between variables related to CEO personality such as observable features, psychological characteristics, social attributes and professionalism modelling how they can affect the performance of employees within an organization.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Author (2025)

1.8 Research Methodology

This chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the methods used in the study, beginning with a philosophical justification for the research approach and followed by a detailed description of the research design. The methodology also covers the development and refinement of data collection instruments, which included a pilot study to pre-test the instruments. Additionally, the chapter discusses how the reliability and validity of these instruments were tested, with a particular focus on ensuring that the instruments were suitable for the main study.

1.8.1 Philosophical Background and Justification

The study adopts a positivist epistemology and an objectivist ontology, both of which influence the approach taken towards data collection and analysis. From a philosophical standpoint, this research aligns with a scientific, objective approach to understanding the relationship between CEO personality and employee performance. By adopting a positivist stance, the research assumes that knowledge is objective and measurable, and that the phenomena being studied can be quantified. The ontology of objectivism reflects the belief that reality exists independent of individual perception and can be measured directly. Additionally, the research

follows an unbiased axiology, ensuring that the researcher does not influence the study's outcomes. In this way, the study seeks to provide a clear and objective assessment of how a CEO's personality affects employee performance in small and medium-sized enterprises in Cameroon.

1.8.2 Research Design

A descriptive research design was employed to explore the impact of CEO personality on employee performance within SMEs in Cameroon. This design is appropriate as it allows for the collection, measurement, and analysis of quantitative data that can effectively establish relationships between the independent and dependent variables. Descriptive research is particularly useful in examining the current status of a phenomenon, and in this case, it helped to answer key research questions and test the hypotheses formulated. The design integrates various components into a logical and coherent framework, ensuring that the research addresses the problem effectively and provides comprehensive insights into the subject matter.

1.8.3 Research Strategy and Method

The research follows a survey experiment strategy, where a series of questions are posed to employees of SMEs to gather data about CEO personality and employee performance. The responses are then analyzed using statistical software, specifically SPSS, for both descriptive and inferential statistics. This strategy is particularly useful for collecting large amounts of data from diverse respondents, allowing for a detailed analysis of patterns and relationships. The quantitative methodology adopted in this study emphasizes the use of statistical techniques to examine and interpret the data. Through this methodology, the study seeks to explain the relationship between CEO personality traits and employee performance in SMEs. The study also follows a deductive approach, wherein hypotheses derived from existing theories are tested through data collection and analysis. This confirmatory approach aims to validate or refute the existing theoretical understanding of the relationship between the two variables under investigation.

1.8.4 Data Analysis

The data collected was analyzed using a range of techniques to ensure the robustness of the findings. Factor analysis was used as a dimension reduction technique to group related variables based on their correlations, simplifying the analysis and making it easier to interpret. The data was then subjected to simple regression analysis using SPSS, which helped to test the hypotheses and identify any significant relationships between the variables. In addition, operationalization was employed to define and measure the research variables—CEO personality and employee performance. The independent variable (CEO personality) was broken down into four latent constructs, including observable features, psychological characteristics, social attributes, and professionalism. Meanwhile, employee performance, the dependent variable, was measured through indicators such as productivity, punctuality, and task reliability. The study also addressed data management issues, such as data cleaning, to remove errors and inconsistencies, and employed strategies to handle missing data, ensuring that the analysis was based on valid and complete information.

1.8.5 Sampling

The target population for this study consists of employees working in SMEs in Yaoundé, Cameroon. To determine the appropriate sample size, a stratified sampling technique was used, ensuring that different sectors within the SME population were adequately represented. The sample size was calculated using a standard formula for an unknown population, resulting in a sample size of 384 respondents. This technique helps to ensure that the sample reflects the broader population and allows for more accurate generalizations. The study used purposive sampling to select participants who met specific criteria, ensuring that the sample included individuals who could provide relevant insights into the impact of CEO personality on employee performance.

1.8.6 Data Collection

Data for this study was collected through both primary and secondary sources. Primary data was gathered using a questionnaire, which was distributed to employees within the selected SMEs. The questionnaire utilized a Likert scale, designed to assess employee perceptions of their CEO's personality and its impact on their performance. Secondary data was sourced from previous research, government reports, and other publications related to the study topic. The combination of primary and secondary data ensures a comprehensive understanding of the research problem from both original and existing sources of information.

1.8.7 Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to strict ethical guidelines to ensure the integrity of the research process. Confidentiality was maintained throughout the study, with participants assured that their responses would not be shared with third parties. Voluntary participation was emphasized, with respondents free to withdraw at any time without penalty. Ethical practices also included avoiding data falsification or fabrication, and ensuring that all data reporting was accurate and transparent. Proper referencing was used to acknowledge the work of other researchers, following the APA citation style, and care was taken to avoid misleading information or biased representation of the research findings.

1.9 Data Analysis

The effects of a CEO's personality on employee performance of SMEs in Cameroon were analysed based on the philosophical underpinnings of positivism epistemology and objectivism ontology. To this effect, the study adopted a hypothetic-deductive approach (Creswell, 2009) to test four [4] main statistical relationships established from the relevant empirical and theoretical literature, particularly in the area of CEO's personality, leadership and employees' performance. The independent variable CEO's personality was operationalized into: Observable features [OF=4], Psychological Characteristics [PC=4], Social Attributes [SA=4], and Professionalism [PR=4] whereas the dependent latent construct was Employees' Performance [EP = 4]. The analytical procedure of the study was concluded based on the following steps: analysis of participants' background information, missing data analysis, dimension reduction, the test of validity [AVE] and reliability [Alpha Cronbach test] and the test of hypotheses using multiple regression analysis.

1.9.1 Missing Data

In data analysis, missing data is a common occurrence due to various reasons, including respondent behavior and data entry issues. Missing data can arise either intentionally (Missing Not At Random, MNAR) or unintentionally (Missing Completely At Random, MCAR). The MCAR hypothesis was tested using Little's test (1988), and the results indicated that the missing data was statistically insignificant, suggesting it occurred randomly. To address missing data, several methods can be employed, such as re-entering the data, deleting outliers, or using statistical techniques like the Expectation Maximization Algorithm (EMA). In this study, the EMA technique was used to handle missing data before conducting further analysis.

1.9.2 Dimension Reduction Analysis [EFA]

Factor analysis is the most commonly used analytic technique for data reduction and refining constructs (Ford, MacCallum, & Tait, 1986). Once missing data has been identified and treated, the next step is to reduce the dimension of the data. It is important to note that not every indicator used in a questionnaire survey constitutes a relevant measurement of what they are expected to measure. Such scenarios are caused by inconsistent measurements. In this study, EFA was conducted for both dependent and independent variables. The independent variable was employee performance. The analysis is intended to identify and remove noise from the data.

To begin, two assumptions must be considered when analysing dimension reduction [EFA]: the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin coefficient which measures sampling adequacy with the coefficient of at least 0.5 [KMO > 0.5] and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity measures the existence of at least one significant correlation with P-Value less than 0.05 [P-Value < 0.05]. It is only after these assumptions are met that the analysis of EFA is worthy. However,

before concluding on the suitability of the indicators involved in the model, the study indicated how constructs were cleaned using a different statistical model.

Based on the aforementioned, the analysis of EFA involving the specific independent latent construct was conducted with the use of the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) technique as the mode of extraction with a defined fixed factor. The rotation method was Promax with Kaiser Normalization converged on 1 iteration. Factor loadings and coefficients were suppressed to 0.4 to minimise the noise in the final factor loadings. The guiding provisions for appropriate factor loadings must not cross-load and must have a coefficient of at least 0.5. Any indicator with a factor loading of less than 0.5 and or is cross-loaded must be rejected. The downsized factor loading revealed the rejection of constructs. The retained Pattern matrix with appropriate factor loadings is as shown below.

Table 1: Promax Matrix

	Component			
	1	2	3	4
OF3	.743			
OF4	.948			
PC1			.715	
PC3			.659	
PC4			.824	
SA1		.569		
SA2		.948		
SA3		.711		
PR1				.754
PR2				.845
PR4				.672

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
 Rotation Method: Promax with Kaiser Normalization.
 a. Rotation converged in 7 iterations.

Source: Author (2025)

1.9.3 KMO and Bartlett's Test

In cognisance of the aforementioned results, the test of the two assumptions of EFA revealed that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy of the study was 0.808 greater than 0.5 [KMO = 0.679 > 0.5] and the Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was Chi-square [X^2] = 937.866 with; Degree of Freedom (DF) = 157 and sig. = 0.00 < 0.01 as shown below:

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.808
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	937.866
	Df	157
	Sig.	.000

Source: Author (2025)

Based on the aforesaid assumptions, EFA was conducted. Four [4] factors were extracted using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) technique with an Eigen value greater than 1[Eigen Value ≥ 1]. Rotation was through Promax. The results revealed Eigenvalues of [5.011, 2.181, 1.938, and 1.180 greater than 1] for the four [4] extracted components. Components with an Eigenvalue of less than 1 were rejected. However, the extracted component accounted for a Total Variance Explained of 66.061% whereas the variance explained by the four [4] components was 27.837%, 12.118%, 10.764% and 6.554% respectively as shown below.

1.9.4 Identification of Outliers and their Treatment

Field (2009) defines an outlier as a unique data value that stands out because it is different from the rest of the data. Outlier management is important in research because the outlying observations can have a substantial impact on the analysis of results. It is therefore important to identify and exclude outliers from a data set before carrying out analysis since it may lead to poor and unreliable results. Outliers can be identified and treated using different statistical methods such as scatter plot graphs, box plot approach and standardized residual method (Z-score). However, in this study outlier was conducted using the box plot methods. This process was carried out repeatedly until no outlier was identified as shown on the boxplot below.

Figure 1: Outliers Identification using Box Plot Method

1.9.5 Test for Normality of data

Skewness is a measure of symmetry or the lack of symmetry in the data set (Field, 2009). A distribution, or data set, is symmetric if it looks the same to the left and right of the center point. Kurtosis on the other hand is a measure of whether the data are peaked or flat relative to a normal distribution (Field, 2009). Skewness and Kurtosis were measured to check if the data set is normally distributed to be able to defend the choice of analysis and to enable generalizability of findings as indicated in the table below.

Table 3: Skewness and Kurtosis

Descriptive Statistics									
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Observable features	128	1.00	3.00	1.9680	.52544	.202	.214	-.512	.425
Psychological characteristics	128	1.33	4.33	2.7031	.73185	.227	.214	-.376	.425
Social attributes	128	1.00	2.50	1.6126	.45675	.128	.214	-1.300	.425
Professionalism	128	1.67	3.33	2.6320	.42129	-.161	.214	-.529	.425
employees' performance	126	1.00	4.40	2.5635	.83308	.222	.216	-.476	.428
Valid N (listwise)	126								

As a general rule of thumb, if skewness is less than -1 or greater than 1, the distribution is highly skewed. If skewness is between -1 and -0.5 or between 0.5 and 1, the distribution is moderately skewed. If skewness is between -0.5 and 0.5, the distribution is approximately symmetric while Kurtosis should be between -2 and +2 for normal Univariate distribution (George & Mallery, 2003). According to the results, observable features, psychological characteristics, social attributes, professionalism and employees' performance are approximately symmetric distributions with coefficients of [.202, .227, .128, .449, and .222]. Positive values of skewness indicate many low scores on the left and negative values indicate many high scores on the right side of the distribution. The Kurtosis values for all the variables fell within the range of ± 2 also implying normal distribution [.425, .425, .425, .425, .425 and .428]. Positive values of kurtosis display many scores on the tail and a pointy distribution (leptokurtic kurtosis) while negative values indicate few scores on the tail and a flat distribution (platykurtic kurtosis).

1.9.6 Multiple Regression Hypotheses Testing

Based on the regression model, the overall descriptive analysis of the model revealed the mean distribution as follows [Employees Performance = 2.5635, observable features = 1.9675, psychological characteristics = 2.7196, social attributes = 1.6171, professionalism] with a total number of observations of [N = 380]. The resulting outputs of the Pearson Moment Correlation revealed that observable features, psychological characteristics, social attributes and professionalism all have a significant statistical relationship with Employees' Performance as shown in the correlation output below.

Table 4: Correlations

		Employees' Performance	observable features	psychological characteristics	social attributes	professionalism
Pearson Correlation	Employees' Performance	1.000	.352	.503	.468	.534
	observable features	.352	1.000	.295	.268	.349
	psychological characteristics	.503	.295	1.000	.215	.161
	social attributes	.468	.268	.215	1.000	.442
	Professionalism	.534	.349	.161	.442	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Employees' Performance	.	.000	.000	.000	.000
	observable features	.000	.	.000	.001	.000
	psychological characteristics	.000	.000	.	.008	.036
	social attributes	.000	.001	.008	.	.000
	Professionalism	.000	.000	.036	.000	.
N	Employees' Performance	380	380	380	380	380
	observable features	380	380	380	380	380
	psychological characteristics	380	380	380	380	380
	social attributes	380	380	380	380	380
	Professionalism	380	380	380	380	380

Based on the analysis of the regression model, the overall predictive power of the model as revealed by the coefficient of Adjusted R Square = 0.485, implies that the predictors in the model relating to observable features, psychological characteristics, social attributes and professionalism accounted for 48.5% of the variation caused on Employees' Performance, as shown below.

Table 5: Model Summary

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.711 ^a	.506	.485	.59777
a. Predictors: (Constant), observable features, psychological characteristics, social attributes and professionalism				
b. Dependent Variable: Employees' Performance				

To ascertain the suitability of the model, ANOVA analysis was conducted and the test of model fit revealed that at Regression model 1, with Sum of Squares = 43.873, Degree of Freedom = 5, F-Test = 24.556, and Mean = 8.775 showed that the model is statistically significant and thus the data fits the model at P-V = 0.000 as shown below

Table 6: ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	43.873	5	8.775	24.556	.000 ^b
	Residual	42.879	120	.357		
	Total	86.752	125			
a. Dependent Variable: Employees' Performance						
b. Predictors: (Constant), observable features, psychological characteristics, social attributes and professionalism						

Based on the test of hypotheses, the study revealed that observable features, psychological characteristics, social attributes and professionalism all have a positive statistical significant influence on Employees' Performance

Table 7: Coefficients

Coefficients ^a										
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-.629	.384		-1.637	.104	-1.389	.132		
	observable features	.089	.112	.056	.792	.0430	-.133	.311	.812	1.232
	psychological characteristic	.409	.088	.356	4.628	.000	.234	.584	.696	1.437
	social attributes	.380	.132	.210	2.873	.005	.118	.643	.774	1.292
	Professionalism	.109	.146	.055	.745	.0458	-.181	.398	.742	1.347
a. Dependent Variable: Employees Performance										

Table 8: Summary of results

Hypotheses	Significant value	Decision / Conclusion
H1: There is a significant and positive relationship between observable features of the CEO and the employees' performance in SMEs	P-value=0.0430< 0.05	Reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant and positive relationship between observable features (OF) of the CEO and the employees' performance (EP) in SMEs.
H2: There is a significant and positive relationship between CEO's psychological characteristics and the employees' performance in SMEs	P-value=0.000< 0.05	Reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant and positive relationship between CEO's psychological characteristics (PC) and the employees' performance (EP) in SMEs
H3: There is a significant and positive relationship between the social attributes of a CEO and the employees' performance in SMEs	P-value=0.005< 0.05	Reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant and positive relationship between the social attributes (SA) of a CEO and the employees' performance (EP) in SMEs
H4: There is a significant and positive relationship between the professionalism of a CEO and the employees' performance in SMEs	P-value=0.0458< 0.05	Reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant and positive relationship between the professionalism (PR) of a CEO and the employees' performance (EP) in SMEs

1.10 Discussion of Findings

The study aimed to explore the influence of various CEO traits on employee performance in SMEs, testing four key hypotheses. The regression analysis confirmed significant positive relationships between all CEO attributes and employee performance, as evidenced by the statistical outputs. Hypothesis 1, which proposed a positive relationship between observable features of the CEO and employee performance, yielded a p-value of 0.0430, which is less than the 0.05 threshold, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This result suggests that observable features such as age, gender, and ethnicity significantly influence employees' performance. Similarly, Hypothesis 2 examined the effect of the CEO's psychological characteristics on employee performance, with a p-value of 0.000, which is well below 0.05. This also led to rejecting the null hypothesis and concluding a significant positive effect of psychological traits like agreeableness, conscientiousness, and emotional stability on employee performance. In Hypothesis 3, the study found a significant positive relationship between the CEO's social attributes (such as being a good listener and always smiling) and employee performance, with a p-value of 0.005. Finally, Hypothesis 4 proposed that the professionalism of a CEO measured by factors like education, previous employment, and punctuality would positively impact employee performance, with a p-value of 0.0458, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis and confirming the significant effect of professionalism on performance. All hypotheses were supported, indicating that CEO characteristics play a crucial role in shaping employee behavior and performance in SMEs.

1.11 Conclusion:

The findings from this study provide compelling evidence that CEO characteristics significantly influence employee performance in SMEs. Statistical tests confirmed the significance of all four proposed relationships. Specifically, observable features (p-value = 0.0430), psychological characteristics (p-value = 0.000), social attributes (p-value = 0.005), and professionalism (p-value = 0.0458) all demonstrated significant positive correlations with employee performance. These results suggest that leadership traits, such as the CEO's personality and social behavior, can motivate employees and enhance organizational performance. Therefore, CEOs who possess positive psychological traits, exhibit professional behaviors, and maintain effective social interactions with their employees are more likely to foster a productive work environment, ultimately contributing to the success of SMEs.

1.12 Recommendations

Based on the findings, several recommendations were made. First, CEOs should work on building cooperative relationships with employees to foster trust and collaboration. Second, a supportive leadership approach should be adopted, where managers offer training and support tailored to individual employee needs. Third, CEOs need to align their leadership style with the expectations of their employees to reduce discrepancies between leadership personality and employee needs. Finally, improving communication and involving employees in decision-making will create a more inclusive and productive work environment.

1.13 Reference

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